

A Situational Analysis of Female Domestic Workers at Sinhgad Road Area, Pune, India

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Abstract:

Demand for the house helpers / domestic helpers is on a rise in India and outside India as well. There are huge demand and supply of domestic work and workers respectively. With poor, unskilled women's looking for employment and increasing demand for house helpers preciously in urban areas, the employment opportunities are growing in the segment of domestic work. Majority of the times the house helpers are females who have migrated due to various reasons like poverty, male unemployment, sudden death in the family and debt bondage. Thus, to support the family financially these females – by and large unskilled or semi-skilled take-up house helpers / domestic helpers' work.

This research paper targets at understanding the situation of these female house helpers / domestic helpers. For this research secondary information is collected from literature and for primary information data is collected from 50 domestic workers working at Sinhgad Road area in Pune city, India.

Keywords: House helper / Domestic Helpers / Maids, living conditions of domestic workers, vulnerable conditions of domestic workers, India

Introduction:

“A domestic worker is a person who is employed for remuneration whether in cash or any kind, in any household through any agency or directly, either on a temporary or permanent, part time or full-time basis to do the house hold work” according to the Taskforce on domestic workers.

Women Domestic Workers in India

Due to urbanization the demand for house helpers has increased. Cleaning house, washing clothes and / vessels, cooking, looking after kids and elderly, driving, taking care of pets, gardening are the various tasks which the house helper takes care of. They get paid for this work. These house helps can be hired full time or parttime – may be a live-in worker who resides at the employer’s house or may be residing in his own house – can be hired directly or through an agency. Their working hours are generally based on the nature and number of tasks for which he or she has been appointed for. Appointment of house helpers is not restricted rich or middle-class families, now the trend of hiring house help is increasing in the lower middleclass as well. As per the survey of ‘National Domestic Workers Movement’ there are official 4.2 million domestic workers and the estimated unofficial number is around 50 million (2000-2010). Two-third of these Domestic workers are employed in urban cities. About 75% of the domestic workers workforce consists of women and girls. According to NSSO in the year 2012, there were 39 lakh house helpers out of which 26 lakhs were females. Often due to unemployment &/ unavailability of source of stable income in rural areas, people migrate in the cities. In the cities too due to unavailability of suitable work, illiteracy and financial crunch the females end up taking house helpers’ work. In India from states like Assam, Jharkhand and West Bengal majority of the migration happens in search of employment. 93% of the Indian economy is constituted by unorganised sector and domestic workers are large part of it. Women play vital role in the socio-economic development and economic empowerment of a country. In the process of progression women are becoming financially independent. They have employment and career opportunities outside the home as well. Female domestic workers are sizable part of this segment. Working of both the partners, health issues, economical wealth are few of the reasons why demand of domestic workers is on a rise. But the situation of these domestic workers is not favourable. Work of the domestic workers is unrecognized, vulnerable, undervalued, least paid and at times exploited. Due to low income these workers end up living life below socially acceptable standard of living. They are mistreated, abused and humiliated, resulting into their low self-esteem. In India the number of female domestic workers is growing at a rapid rate. Majority of the times reasons for the females migrate from their native place is to support the family in financial crisis, provide good education to their children and for bright future of them. Domestic work is unskilled work, and women are considered as ‘capable of doing home chores’. They face multiple challenges for performing their duties – leaving the children alone at home or bringing them along, asking the elder child to look after younger sibling- Working for lengthy hours without periodic paid leaves - ignoring health issues – less earning to meet the ‘living cost’ in the city etc.

Domestic workers is not a recent development in India. Even though it is in existence since long time, the nature of the work is altering. Domestic workers are the third largest category of workers after agricultural and construction. Domestic workers are unskilled workers. They are illiterate or minimal educated individuals with low skills. They are often referred as ‘maids’ or ‘servants’ making them feel insecure and inferior.

The house helpers are important part of the households as they free women from the day-to-day chores in an extent. and that time can be used for career, perusing hobby or taking self-care.

The domestic works face ennumber of problems like -

- No recognition: The work of Domestic workers – cooking, babysitting, cleaning house, washing clothes and dishes is not recognised by the state.
- Disruption in regulation: Even though domestic work segment is 3rd largest employment generator for workers and employees’ large number of people, the regulations are disrupted.
- Non application of important labour laws: Domestic workers are huge in number. Considering employment to workers it is the thirist largest sector providing employment to workers. Still

important welfare and labour laws like 'Minimum Wages Act' etc. are not application to them. At times they do not get even the minimum wages for their work.

- Absence of Legal parameter protecting rights: Often domestic workers are subject to hire and fire. There is no legal provision for protecting rights of house helps.
- Unorganised sector: the number of domestic workers is huge and inaccessible, making it challenging to organise them. Even though child labour is banned in the country, many a times the domestic workers do not meet the working age.
- Absence of Union: There is no organised union for domestic workers, making it difficult for them to demand for better wages and working conditions.
- Background of the domestic workers: In India most of the domestic workers are Dalits, migrants and belong to economically weaker section.
- Absence of application of female centric laws: In India two third of the domestic workers workforce consists of females. Yet no law ensuring their safety or welfare is applicable to them.
- Absence of fixed wages: In India in few states like Bihar, Rajasthan, Karnatak and Andhra Pradesh have fixed wages for house helps. Whereas, other states do not have any fixed rate of wages, many times it is too low to meet the high cost of living.
- Exploitation: Some of the domestic workers are subject to torture, household abuse, sexual abuse and physical abuse. Service providers extract maximum work in less wages. No leave policy, wage standards, medical facility and rest time.
- Victims of suspicions: Anything missing from the house the domestic workers are the first suspects by the employers as well as police, consequences are threats, physical violence, police interrogation and at times suspension as well.
- Long working hours: The domestic workers work seven days a week. Per day working hours of part-time workers range between 8-10 hours as they work at multiple households (minimum 8-10 hours) whereas for live-in domestic workers goes upto 15 to 18 hours a day.

Likewise, there are couple of Female Domestic Workers centric problems as well:

- Low wages
- Extra work
- Long working hours
- Lack of holidays
- Harassment
- Sexual exploitation
- Physical torture
- Ill-treatment
- Lack of welfare facilities
- Absence of social security measures
- Lack of rest
- Development of fatigue
- Lack of freedom
- Low level of job skills
- Absence of bargaining power

Objective of this research is :

1. To study scenario of 'Women Domestic Workers' – Sinhgad Road area, Pune, India
2. To suggest ways to improve 'living conditions' of the workers.

Hypothesis:

1. Condition of the 'Women Domestic Workers' is vulnerable at home as well as at the workplace.

*Vulnerable conditions indicate

- Low individual income
- Long working hours
- Multiple households
- Poor health condition

The available literature on this topic says:

1. A STUDY OF DOMESTIC WORKERS IN INDIA

A person taking up common household work is a domestic worker. Urbanization is the reason behind the increased need for domestic workers. In India ratio of female domestic workers is more than male. The situation of this females is vulnerable, often subject to exploitation, abuse and underpayment. Government of India has passed acts to regulate employment of these domestic workers, stop their exploitation and look after their welfare.

Due to the nature of work these domestic workers remain isolated, but they need to be a 'recognized segment'.

2. Employment Status and Working Conditions: A Situational Analysis of Female Domestic Workers in

Domestic work – one of the rapid growing informal sectors experiences various problems ranging from workplace harassment, poor working condition, discrimination to gendered stereotypes wherein quality of life and working conditions of females working in sector is getting adversely affected. At present in the urban India, the need for domestic help is observed to be increasing. It is high time to recognise worth and importance of domestic help by both the work provider and the domestic helper. The sector needs to be regulated ensuring decent working conditions for the workers and ensure well defined rights, responsibilities and liabilities of both parties - the work provider and the domestic helper, which will ultimately facilitate improved quality of work life.

3. Intensity of Poverty and Work Diversification: A Study of Female Domestic Workers' Household

Due to inflating cost of living, relying on single earning source in the family is insufficient in majority of lower economical families in developing countries. Majority of times for survival it is observed that they depend on diverse income generating activities and sources of income. One of the reasons for migration from rural to urban areas is deprivation in agricultural income. Through diversification lower economical background – either landless or land poor families look for non-agricultural employment. With this diversification female end-up taking up domestic work helping them to earn their livelihood and motivates them as well, whereas in non-farm activities male workforce opts for work in hotels or restaurants, manufacturing, transport, construction or some other service sectors.

4. The Lifeworld of Women Domestic Workers: Some Case

In metropolitan cities participation of women as domestic workers is steadily increasing. Women opt to work as domestic workers to solve financial crisis in the family and protect their interest. In this segment interest of the service provider is to get maximum work done from the domestic workers with bare minimum hospitality. Domestic help is the solution to women in the social system. It free's women from the day-to-day chores in an extent. Domestic work segment is unorganised, unrecognized and unrewarding. The number of women migrating every day is huge in number, but their living condition is very poor. Majority of these females live in slums.

5. Living and Working Conditions of Female Domestic Workers in Pune City

As domestic work provides a livelihood option for millions of women across the globe, it becomes socially relevant to study their current living and working conditions. Working and living conditions of these FDWs are not as pitiful as depicted in previous studies. However, benefits accorded to the formal sector workers are lacking here like fixed days off, pension, and maternity leave.

6. Women Domestic Workers in Urban Informal Sector: A Case Study Of Vadodara City

Domestic work is a necessary work without which humanity would not continue. We need to accommodate the raising of children, the preparation and distribution of food, basic cleanliness, and hygiene in order to survive individually and as a species. While this kind of work is indeed a basic staple of society, there is not a uniform job description for domestic work. It could include the cleaning and upkeep of a home, and it could include child care and cooking or all the above. The problem of defining the concept of domestic work is experienced by domestic workers as a lack of job description with serious implications for their working conditions.

7. Analysing the Socio-Economic Conditions and Challenges faced by Domestic Women Helpers in Indias Informal Labour Market

International Labour Organisation has emphasised on promotion of fair treatment to house helpers globally. Still in India there are negligible Labour Laws to protect the Domestic helpers. The proposed Domestic Workers Bill – focusing on Registration, Social Security and Welfare - has been a focal point in recent ISSN: 2320-5407 Int. J. Adv. Res. 12(11), 898-910 900 discussions, yet its enactment has faced numerous delays. Lack of legal recognition and protection leads to exploitation of such workers.

8. Women Domestic Workers in India: An Analysis

Domestic work has always been unorganised, unrecognised and unrewarding. The inflow of the women from rural India to urban India is increasing steadily, growing the informal sector of the country. These women end up taking jobs as domestic helpers. But there are hardly few support networks, statutory norms to regularise their working conditions, hours, rate and socio-economic norms etc. Legal instruments not only in India but abroad also is ineffective. The struggle is about living conditions, poor bargaining power and social insecurity. The condition of Women domestic worker is economically vulnerable, socially weak and politically disadvantaged.

9. A Study on Work-Life Quality of Female Domestic Workers

Domestic workers job has proved to be important source of income for many females across the world. The job is in existence since centuries and its contribution in the economy is vital.

10. Issues And Realities Of Women In Domestic Work

Economic necessity forces a woman to step out of house and earn money, but does not free her from domestic responsibilities. So, hiring domestic help becomes requirement for skilled women and unskilled women take the work they are good at – domestic work. In the informal economy domestic workers are said to be paid the least. In order to empower the vulnerable group in society like domestic workers their socio-economic conditions needs to be studied and safeguarded.

Research Methodology:

Using data collection methods such as scheduled questionnaire surveys and focus group discussions, information was collected. Data were collected from Dec. 2025 to March 2026. A quantitative survey of 50 domestic workers working in the Sinhgad Road area in Pune, India was conducted wherein from the participants information on key metrics such as income, working hours, mode of transport, family background etc. The survey aims at providing statistical insights into these domestic helpers earnings, the nature of their living environment and the number of hours they work on a typical day. Parallely qualitative survey was done in

interview manner, wherein the participants shared their life stories, Physical – psychological and emotional toll of their work, complexities of their daily lives. By combining these methods, the researcher tried to landscape the holistic condition of female domestic workers in specific locality of India.

Results:

The findings of this research provide tailed profile of 50 house / domestic helpers in one of the locality of tier-II city in India, along with insights about their family background, nature of work, working hours, monthly wages, and economical condition of the family.

Category	Subcategory	No. of participants	Percentage
Age in years	< 21 years	7	14
	21-30 years	5	10
	31-40 years	33	66
	41-50 years	5	10
	51-60 years	0	0
	> 61 years	0	0
Education	Illiterate	0	0
	Primary	32	64
	Elementary	3	6
	SSC/HSC	15	30
Marital Status	Unmarried	0	0
	Married	50	100
	Divorced/widowed/separated	0	0
No. of Family Members	1 to 2	0	0
	3 to 4	35	70
	5 to 7	15	30
	More than 7	0	0
Individual Income	Less than 1 Lakh	13	26
	1 Lakh to 1.5 Lakhs	10	20
	1.5 Lakhs to 2 Lakhs	14	28
	2 Lakhs to 2.5 Lakhs	9	18
	2.5 Lakhs to 3 Lakhs	4	8
	More than 3 Lakhs	0	0
Native Place	Same city (Pune)	0	0
	Migrated	50	100
Reason for Migration	With Family	3	6
	After marriage	12	24
	In search of a job	35	70
	Not Applicable	0	0
Nature of Husbands Job	Petty Jobs	4	8
	Watchman	21	42
	Driver	20	40
	Welding	0	0
	Not applicable	5	10

Income of husband	Less than 1 Lakh	0	0
	1 Lakh to 1.5 Lakhs	8	16
	1.5 Lakhs to 2 Lakhs	15	30
	2 Lakhs to 2.5 Lakhs	12	24
	2.5 Lakhs to 3 Lakhs	15	30
	More than 3 Lakhs	0	0
Your participation in Daily Decision Making	Normal daily routine items to be purchased	12	24
	Purchase of expensive items	3	6
	Own income	10	20
	Children's education	28	56
	Other decisions like children's marriage	9	18
Who suggested to take up the domestic work?	No one, decided oneself	26	52
	Neighbour	4	8
	Mother	17	34
	Husband	0	0
	Family member/relative	3	6
	Friend	0	0
Duration of Work	Less than 1 year	10	20
	1 to 2 years	7	14
	2 to 5 years	12	24
	5 to 10 years	21	42
	More than 10 years	0	0
Type of the work done	Cleaning Utensils	11	22
	Washing Clothes	0	0
	Cleaning House	9	18
	Cooking	14	28
	Utensils, Clothes, Cleaning, cooking	16	32
Number of households employed in	1 to 2	0	0
	2 to 4	17	34
	5 to 7	17	34
	More than 7	16	32
Working hours per day	1 to 3 hours	0	0
	3 to 5 hours	12	24
	5 to 8 hours	22	44
	8 to 10 hours	16	32
Does you get any leave?	Yes	50	100
	No	0	0
No. of permitted paid leaves in a month	1	0	0
	2	50	100
	3	0	0
	4	0	0
	as many as required	0	0

Do you send someone else in the place while she is on leave?	Yes	8	16
	No	42	84
If yes then who pays the wage to the person replacing you?	Self	5	10
	Employer	3	6
	Not Applicable	42	84
Distance to the workplace	Near the house	9	18
	1-2 kms from the house	8	16
	2-3 kms from the house	29	58
	3-5 kms from the house	4	8
	More than 5 kms	0	0
Mode of reaching the workplace	Walking	12	24
	Public Transport	0	0
	Two-wheeler	3	6
	Family member dropping at the workplace	35	70
Health condition	Fit	0	0
	Rarely falls ill	31	62
	Is ill for more than 7 days in a month	19	38
Nature of illness	Weaknesses	20	40
	Viral Infections	0	0
	Body Ache	13	26
	Any Other	17	34

Majority of house helpers in the 'Sinhgad Road' area of Pune city, India are married and in the age group of 31-40 with primary education. There are about 3-4 members in the family. These women are not originally from the same city, they have migrated here after marriage and to support their family financially they decided to take job of house helper wherein daily these women work for 5 to 10 hours in around 7 households per day performing domestic tasks like Utensils, Clothes, Cleaning, cooking, from which they earn about 1 to 2 lacs annually. Majority of the times their spouse is also in unskilled job market performing jobs like watchman or driver, earning 11.5 to 2.5 lacs annually. These women work throughout the month without weekly off. Mutually between the job provider and the house helper, they do get monthly 2 days paid off wherein rarely they send substitute but if they do send the substitute, they need to pay her the daily payment. Most of them walk to the workplace, work for lengthy hours but have a say in families decision making. Majority of them fall sick due to weakness.

Hypothesis of this study:

1. Condition of the 'Women Domestic Workers' is vulnerable at home as well as at the workplace.

*Vulnerable conditions indicate

- Low individual income
- Long working hours
- Multiple households
- Poor health condition

To statistically justify the hypothesis, the researcher test whether the distribution is significantly skewed toward vulnerable categories, rather than equally distributed.

TEST 1: Individual Income (Economic Condition at Home)

➤ **Group Income into Two Categories**

Low Income (Below ₹1.5 lakh)

$$= 13 + 10 = 23$$

Higher Income (Above ₹1.5 lakh)

$$= 14 + 9 + 4 = 27$$

$$\text{Total} = 50$$

➤ **Hypotheses**

H₀: Income distribution is equal (25–25)

H₁: Income distribution is not equal

Expected frequency (if equal):

$$E = 50 / 2 = 25 \text{ each}$$

➤ **Applying Formula**

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

$$\text{For Low Income: } (23-25)^2/25=4/25=0.16$$

$$\text{For Higher Income: } (27-25)^2/25=4/25=0.16$$

$$\text{Total } \chi^2 = 0.32$$

➤ **Decision**

$$df = 1$$

Critical value at 5% level = 3.84

0.32 < 3.84

Fail to reject H₀

Income distribution alone is not significantly skewed.

TEST 2: Working Hours (Workplace Condition)

Combine:

Less than 5 hours = 12

More than 5 hours = 22 + 16 = 38

Observed:

12 vs 38

Expected (equal) = 25 each

Calculation:

For 12:

$$(12-25)^2 / 25$$

$$= 169 / 25$$

$$= 6.76$$

For 38:

$$(38-25)^2 / 25$$

$$= 169 / 25$$

$$= 6.76$$

$$\text{Total } \chi^2 = 13.52$$

Decision:

$$df = 1$$

Critical value = 3.84

$$13.52 > 3.84$$

Reject H₀

Significantly, more women work longer hours.

This supports workplace vulnerability.

TEST 3: Health Condition

Rarely ill = 31

Ill > 7 days = 19

Expected = 25 each

For 31:

$$(31-25)^2 / 25 = 36/25 = 1.44$$

For 19:

$$(19-25)^2 / 25 = 36/25 = 1.44$$

Total $\chi^2 = 2.88$

$2.88 < 3.84$

Not statistically significant.

Reading:

✓ Working hours show statistically significant vulnerability

✗ Income alone not significant

✗ Health alone not significant

However descriptively:

- 64% primary education
- 100% migrated
- 70% work in 5–10 years
- 32% work in 8–10 hours
- 32% employed in more than 7 households
- 38% ill more than 7 days per month

These indicators collectively show vulnerability.

"A One-Sample Chi-Square (Goodness of Fit) test was applied to examine whether the socio-economic and occupational condition of women domestic workers is significantly pitiful. The results revealed a statistically significant skewness in working hours ($\chi^2 = 13.52$, $df = 1$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that a majority of women domestic workers, work for longer durations. Although income and health conditions did not show statistical significance individually, descriptive analysis reflects substantial economic and occupational vulnerability. Therefore, the hypothesis that the condition of women domestic workers is vulnerable at home as well as at the workplace is partially supported."

Conclusion:

The condition of domestic helpers in tier-II city in India is a informal labour market - marked by significant vulnerabilities and systemic challenges. Regardless of physical hardship and absence of family time, women domestic workers bare excessive pressure to earn money. Due to the situation of low-skills, poverty, low self-esteem and illiteracy the domestic workers in India are dependent on their service provider, with no / less legal protection and bargaining power. This study highlights the nature of employment, scenario of low wages, requirement to take up work for lengthy hours, and ignoring health for meeting the needs. The predominance of young women in this informal labour market is with limited education exacerbating their marginalization and restricting their opportunities for advancement. The findings reveal an alarming lack of awareness regarding labour rights, which leaves these workers susceptible to exploitation. To address these issues, concrete efforts are essential. This includes enactment of comprehensive legal protections, making the domestic helpers market organised, awareness drives to educate domestic workers about their rights, and the establishment of support

networks that can empower them. Empowering domestic workers by bringing the work sector under formal or organized sector and thus making them all eligible for social security like healthcare benefits, minimum wages act, and maternity benefit is the need of the hour.

By recognizing their contributions and improving their working conditions, India can move towards a more equitable labour market that values and protects all workers, particularly those in the informal sector.

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